

TEACHERS' KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE, AND CAPABILITY TO INTEGRATE CHILD PROTECTION POLICY (CPP) INTO THEIR CLASSROOM PRACTICES: BASIS FOR FACULTY CAPACITY BUILDING PROGRAM

Floro T. del Pilar III, MEM

Child Protection Committee Coordinator, Research Committee Coordinator, Guinayang National High School, San Mateo, Rizal, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11117956>

ABSTRACT

This study determined the knowledge, attitude, and capability to integrate the Child Protection Policy (CPP) into classroom practices of the junior high school teachers of the district of San Mateo, division of Rizal. The study utilized the descriptive qualitative research design which, according to Calderon (2006), involves the systematic collection, analysis, categorization, and tabulation of data about present conditions, practices, processes, trends, and cause-effect relationships. The results revealed that the teachers' level of knowledge about the child protection policy is verbally interpreted as 'knowledgeable', their attitude towards the integration of CPP is verbally interpreted as 'agree', and their level of capability to integrate CPP into their classroom is verbally interpreted as 'capable'. Moreover, there is no significant difference between the teachers' knowledge about CPP and their profiles except in the schools where they teach. There is a significant difference between the teachers' attitude and their age, the subject they teach, and the number of years in service. Except for the school where they teach and their number of years in service, there is no significant difference between their capability to integrate CPP into their classroom practices and their age, civil status, the subject they teach, their highest educational attainment, and position. It can be concluded that after more than a decade of the implementation of the Child Protection Policy, the teachers' knowledge, attitude, and capability to integrate CPP into their classroom practices can still be improved. The significant differences according to profiles must be considered in drafting focused training programs.

Keywords: *Knowledge of Child Protection Policy, attitude, capability, integrate*

INTRODUCTION

The Philippine National Baseline Study on Violence Against Children (2016) found that 80% of Filipino children experienced some violence at home, school, employment, in the community, or while dating. The DepEd issued the Child Protection Policy (CPP) in 2012 specifically to address child abuse. The CPP, DepEd Order no. 40 s. 2012, protects children's well-being and ensures that abuse, neglect, and exploitation are caught and punished. The CPP becomes a set of norms and culture that transforms schools into a secure learning environment in which children's dignity and security are prioritized. The teachers' role is the most critical one among the different stakeholders to successfully implement CPP (Kempe Foundation, 2023). Teachers are generally the first to spot abuse or neglect since they directly interact with students. The CPP also emphasized curricular integration as the curriculum should teach students their rights and responsibilities. The 2nd paragraph of section 11 of the CPP states that "They shall likewise employ means which enhance the skills and pedagogy in integrating and teaching children's rights in the classroom." In her study, Morante (2017) identified the integration of child rights and responsibilities in all subjects as a CPP implementation intervention. Thus, it is important to investigate the knowledge, attitude, and capabilities of the teachers to integrate CPP into their subject lessons. Although there have been quite a few research that investigated the teachers' knowledge and the teachers' perceptions of CPP, there has been no study yet on the teachers' capability to integrate the policy into their classrooms nor has there been any study that investigated together the teachers' knowledge, attitude, and capability.

Research Questions

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of age, civil status, highest educational attainment, school deployment, subject department, position, and years in service?
2. What is their level of knowledge about the CPP?
3. What is their attitude towards the integration of CPP into their classrooms?
4. What is their level of capability to integrate CPP into their classrooms?
5. Is there any significant difference in the level of knowledge, attitude, and capability of teachers when grouped according to their profile?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilized the descriptive quantitative research method which is defined by Calderon (2006) as a design that involves the systematic collection, analysis, categorization, and tabulation of data about present conditions, practices, processes, trends, and cause-effect relationships. The design made appropriate and precise interpretations of the gathered data with the use of statistical methods. Moreover, this

approach determined the current state of facts within a studied group, producing descriptions of the group's quantitative overall features outcomes.

Research Respondents

The respondents of this study are the teachers employed at the Junior High Schools in the District of San Mateo, Rizal. There are 6 Junior high schools in the district and they all participated in this study through a stratified sampling method. The six schools are Pintong Bukawe National High School, San Mateo National High School, Jose F. Diaz Memorial National High School, Ampid National High School, Silangan National High School, and Guinayang National High School. The total sample size of the teachers in the six schools for the school year 2023-2024 that were part of the study is 216. The Cochran finite population correction formula was used to determine the appropriate sample size population.

Research Instrument

The researcher utilized a researcher-made questionnaire which was based on the Child Protection Policy and is composed of two parts. Part 1 collected the teachers' demographics, including their age, civil status, school, the subject being taught, highest educational attainment, position, and the number of years in service. Part II dealt with the level of knowledge about CPP, their attitude about integrating CPP into their classroom practices, and their capability to integrate CPP into their classroom practices. Six experts validated the questionnaire using the Survey Instrument Validation Rating Scale by Oducado (2020). Most of them commented on how the teacher's knowledge about CPP is not considered a perception, so during the title defense, the title of the study was changed. The questionnaire was pilot-tested on 53 teachers who were not part of the study. To check the reliability or the internal consistency of the questionnaire, Cronbach's alpha was used through SPSS version 23. The result yielded a Cronbach's alpha of 0.982 which is greater than the threshold of 0.70 (acceptable) indicating that the reliability of the questionnaire is verbally interpreted as 'excellent'.

Data Analysis

After importing all information from Google Forms, the researcher used the following statistical treatment of data:

- To present the profile of the respondents, percentage and frequency were used.
 - To present the teachers' knowledge, attitude, and capability to integrate the Child Protection Policy into their classrooms, mean and grand mean were used.
 - Kruskal Wallis H-Test was used to know if there is a significant difference in the level of knowledge, attitude, and capability of teachers to integrate the Child Protection Policy into their classrooms when grouped according to profile.
-

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The respondents were profiled according to age, civil status, highest educational attainment, school deployment, subject department, position, and years in service. Tables 1 to 7 show the profile of the respondents. The respondents' level of knowledge of the Child Protection Policy, their attitude, and their capability to integrate the policy into their classrooms are shown in Tables 8,9, and 10 respectively. Tables 11-17 show the significant difference in the level of knowledge, attitude, and capability to integrate child protection policy when respondents are grouped according to profile.

Table 1. Respondents' Age Group

Age Group	Frequency	Percentage (%)
20-25 years old	9	4.17
26-30 years old	33	15.28
31-35 years old	39	18.06
36-40 years old	48	22.22
41-45 years old	35	16.20
46-50 years old	26	12.04
51 and above	26	12.04
Total	216	100.00

The most number of respondents comes from the 36-40 years old group while the least number comes from the 20-25 years old age group. Recent graduates often seek practical experience in the private sector to enhance their credentials before they apply to the public sector. This is seen by the least number of respondents by age group. Thus, it is not surprising that most teacher respondents in this study fall within the age range of 31 to 40 years old, given that these individuals have amassed a substantial number of graduate-level units and years of experience, which enables them to confidently apply for positions in public schools.

Table 2. Respondents' Civil Status

Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
single	66	30.56
married	143	66.20
widow/widower	4	1.85
separated/annulled	3	1.39
Total	216	100.00

Most of the respondents are married while the least number of respondents come from the separated/annulled group. Public teaching is a secure and enduring occupation, which provides teachers with the stability necessary to enter marriage. The consistent income derived from this profession is dependable, thus enhancing its appeal. This aligns

with the findings of Zabala and Lachica (2018), who claimed that it was typical for most Filipinos to marry once they have secured stable and long-term employment. Hence, it is anticipated that a significant proportion of teachers were already in a state of matrimony.

Table 3. Respondents' Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage (%)
BSE/BSED	49	22.69
BS with CPE units	8	3.70
with MAED/MSE/MAT units	118	54.63
MAED/MSE/MAT/MPA graduate	30	13.89
with Ed.D/ Ph.D or units	6	2.78
Others	5	2.31
Total	216	100.00

Most instructors hold a Bachelor's degree in education, supplemented by coursework completed in master's degree programs. When all is said and done, educators are living examples of a passion for education and ongoing professional growth. In their research, Vural and Basaran (2021) concluded that teachers pursue master's degrees for a variety of reasons, including the pursuit of personal growth or self-improvement in the field of education, the advancement of their careers, the development of their professional skills, and the acquisition of in-depth information in the industry to which they belong.

Table 4. Respondents' School Deployment

School	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Ampid NHS	35	16.20
Guinayang NHS	28	12.96
Jose F. Diaz NHS	20	9.26
Pintong Bukawe NHS	9	4.17
San Mateo NHS	73	33.80
Silangan NHS	51	23.61
Total	216	100.00

The biggest number of respondents comes from San Mateo National High School while the smallest comes from Pintong Bukawe National High School. There are a total of six junior high schools in the district, strategically located to cater to students from the barangay and neighboring barangays. At first, the district consisted solely of San Mateo National High School.

Table 5. Respondents' Subject Department

Subject Department	Frequency	Percentage (%)
English	27	12.50
Filipino	27	12.50
Mathematics	18	8.33
TLE/ICT	30	13.89
Science	34	15.74
ESP	24	11.11
Social Studies	34	15.74
MAPEH	22	10.19
Total	216	100.00

The table shows that all the subjects taught in junior high schools are represented in this study. The largest number of teachers who responded to the questionnaire are teachers of Science and Social studies, and it is noteworthy that these subjects often need a heightened awareness of the CPP. Mathematics, on the other hand, is one subject too technical that it could be hard to look for a connection between the learning competency of the subject and the policies that involve child protection.

Table 6. Respondents' Position

Position	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Teacher I	133	61.57
Teacher II	39	18.06
Teacher III	37	17.13
Master Teacher	7	3.24
Total	216	100.00

The majority of the respondents are Teacher 1 while only 7 are Master Teachers. Although there has been a faster rate of promotion for teachers in recent years, many teachers continue to experience a lack of progress in their professional growth. Pagayanan (2021) defines career advancement stagnation as the state of being stuck in the same teaching job for over 5 years without any changes in duties or responsibilities.

Table 7. Respondents' Years in Service

Number of Years in Service	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1-5 years	65	30.09
6-10 years	74	34.26
11-15 years	37	17.13
16 years and above	40	18.52
Total	216	100.00

The table indicates that a significant proportion of the participants had been employed as educators in public schools for a duration of 10 years or less. Out of the total of 216 responders, only 77 had been engaged in teaching for a period exceeding 11 years. It is well acknowledged that instructors require further exposure to the profession to acquire expertise. Podolsky and Kini (2016) discovered that, in general, teachers became more successful as they gained experience. Nevertheless, the mere passage of time does not inherently result in the improvement of all teachers or the transformation of less-competent teachers into effective ones.

Table 8. Respondents' Level of Knowledge about the Child Protection Policy

Level of Knowledge about Child Protection Policy	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
The effects of child abuse and neglect on the development and well-being of children	3.69	Knowledgeable
The roles and responsibilities of a teacher in CPP	3.65	Knowledgeable
The different forms of child abuse and neglect according to the CPP	3.64	Knowledgeable
The provisions for ensuring the confidentiality and privacy of information related to child abuse cases	3.58	Knowledgeable
The presence of the Child Protection Committee and its functions within the school	3.58	Knowledgeable
The different signs of child abuse and neglect according to the CPP	3.57	Knowledgeable
The purpose of DepEd Order No. 40 s. 2012	3.56	Knowledgeable
The different ways to promote CPP	3.55	Knowledgeable
Consequences for teachers who fail to report suspected child abuse cases	3.51	Knowledgeable
The prevention strategies for child abuse or neglect	3.50	Moderate Knowledge
The reporting procedures for suspected cases of child abuse or neglect	3.48	Moderate Knowledge
The available support services and resources for child protection in the school and the community	3.44	Moderate Knowledge
The intervention strategies for child abuse or neglect	3.38	Moderate Knowledge
The different ways to integrate CPP into my teaching principles	3.38	Moderate Knowledge
Other existing laws and policies connected with CPP	3.36	Moderate Knowledge
Grand Mean:	3.52	Knowledgeable

Legend: 1.00-1.50 Not Knowledgeable; 1.51-2.50 Limited Knowledge; 2.51-3.50 Moderate Knowledge; 3.51-4.50 Knowledgeable; and 4.51-5.00 Highly Knowledgeable

Out of the 15 items, 9 are verbally interpreted as knowledgeable while 6 are moderately knowledgeable. The teachers' knowledge of the effects of child abuse and neglect on the development and well-being of children has the highest mean which is

3.69 which is verbally interpreted as 'knowledgeable'. On the other hand, the teachers' knowledge of the other existing laws and policies connected with CPP has the lowest mean which is 3.36 which is verbally interpreted as 'moderate knowledge'. It can be observed that the teachers generally assess their knowledge about the CPP as 'knowledgeable' with a grand mean of 3.52. Thus, more than a decade after its implementation, the junior high school teachers of the District of San Mateo are now knowledgeable about the CPP.

The findings of this research align with those of Rabina (2019) and Asio (2020), who similarly concluded that while the teachers surveyed possess sufficient understanding of the CPP, they are unfamiliar with its legislative framework and reporting mechanisms as they pertain to its implementation. In the research conducted by Bayucca (2020), the teacher participants demonstrated a comprehensive comprehension of the CPP. Abroad, McGarry and Buckley (2013) showed that although only a few of their participants express a level of assurance in their capacity to recognize and address child safety concerns, their participants in Ireland are knowledgeable about child protection systems in their country as this was part of their studies in college. In the present study, the respondents' mean score of 3.52 is only marginally higher than the threshold of 'moderate knowledge' by 0.02 which is not acceptable given that the implementation of child protection policy is already more than a decade old.

Teachers' "knowledge" of the CPP is praiseworthy; however, it is critical to remember that the policy was initiated in 2012, marking its twelfth anniversary. Within that time frame, educators ought to have acquired a "High Degree of Knowledge" regarding the CPP. Furthermore, although the teachers' low mean score in 'Other existing laws and policies connected to CPP is to be expected, every effort must be made to ensure that they have an in-depth understanding of these policies and laws so that they can carry out their responsibilities as CPP implementers more effectively. Freda Briggs (2020) underscores the need for teachers to have the requisite knowledge of child protection to fulfill their role of safeguarding the welfare of minors.

Table 9. The Respondents' Attitude about the Integration of CPP in their Classrooms

Attitude Toward Integrating Child Protection Policy Into Your Classrooms	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Integrating CPP into my classrooms will benefit my students	4.10	Agree
Integrating CPP in my classroom is important	4.09	Agree
The CPP aligns with the values, ethics, and culture of the school	4.06	Agree
The integration of CPP will positively impact the overall school culture and environment	4.05	Agree
Integrating CPP in my lessons aligns with my values as a teacher	4.04	Agree
Integrating CPP into my lessons will create a safe and supportive learning environment	4.03	Agree
The integration of CPP will promote the holistic development of the students	4.03	Agree

Integrating CPP into lessons is a good collaborating activity among colleagues, specifically in sharing ideas and strategies	4.01	Agree
Integrating CPP will enhance the overall learning experience of the students	4.00	Agree
Integrating CPP makes my lessons more relevant and engaging for my students	3.97	Agree
The CPP inclusion improves the value of my lesson	3.96	Agree
Integrating CPP in my lessons will develop necessary life skills in my students	3.96	Agree
I have confidence that integrating CPP into my lessons will contribute to its successful implementation	3.95	Agree
The time and effort I use to integrate CPP into my lessons make me a better teacher	3.93	Agree
The CPP is relevant to the subject/s that I teach	3.90	Agree
Grand Mean:	4.00	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.50 Strongly Disagree; 1.51-2.50 Disagree; 2.51-3.50 Neutral; 3.51-4.50 Agree; and 4.51-5.00 Strongly Agree

In all 15 concepts, the teachers' mean is verbally interpreted as 'agree'. The highest mean is 4.10 which is 'Integrating Child Protection Policy into my classroom will benefit my students' while the lowest at 3.90 is 'the Child Protection Policy is relevant to the subject/s that I teach'. Overall, the table demonstrates that teachers exhibit an optimistic attitude toward integrating the CPP in their classrooms. It is crucial for students to feel comfortable and protected within the confines of the classroom because most of their time is spent there. The result of the current study is in line with the research of Dela Fuente (2021) where her paper concluded that not only do teachers have adequate knowledge about the Child Protection Policy, but they also have a positive view about its implementation in schools. This result is the same as the study of Baronia (2020) where he found out that teachers are aware of the importance of the promotion of children's welfare.

The mean score for the significance of CPP in the subjects they teach is the lowest among all 15 concepts. It is comprehensible that while integrating CPP may appear straightforward in certain disciplines, such as values education and social science, it may prove challenging or even unattainable in others due to their excessively technical nature such as mathematics. However, Section 11, paragraph 2 of the Child Protection Policy requires schools to strengthen their pedagogical base and ability to integrate children's rights into classroom learning. The CPP must be enforced by all teachers, regardless of their subject.

Table 10. The Respondents' Level of Capability to Integrate Child Protection Policy in their Classroom Practices

Level of Capability to Integrate Child Protection Policy Into Your Classroom Practices	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Integration of CPP into the classroom rules and regulations	3.88	Capable
Encouragement of students to report any concerns they may have about their own safety or the safety of their classmates.	3.88	Capable

Capability to effectively engage students in discussions about child protection topics	3.79	Capable
Inclusion of CCP in classroom routines	3.76	Capable
Ability to communicate the CPP topics to the level of the students	3.72	Capable
Selection of specific CPP topics for integration into the daily lessons	3.71	Capable
Regular review and updating of classroom rules to promote safety and respect	3.71	Capable
Adaptation of teaching methods to include child protection policies	3.69	Capable
Proactive addressing of potential risks and hazards in the classroom environment	3.68	Capable
Planning of age-appropriate lessons that effectively convey Child Protection Policies to students	3.66	Capable
Utilization of CPP-integrated motivation activities	3.64	Capable
Preparation of lesson activities for CPP integration	3.63	Capable
Provision CPP-sensitive examples for the students	3.62	Capable
Development of assessment materials incorporated with CPP topics	3.57	Capable
Researching appropriate references for CPP topics effectively to student	3.53	Capable
Grand Mean:	3.70	Capable

Legend: 1.00-1.50 Not Capable; 1.51-2.50 Less Capable; 2.51-3.50 Moderately Capable; 3.51-4.50 Capable; and 4.51-5.00 Highly Capable

In all 15 items, the teacher's capability mean is verbally interpreted as 'capable'. The highest mean is for the 'capability to integrate child protection policies into the classroom rules and regulations', and the 'I encourage students to report any concerns they may have about their own safety or the safety of their classmates' which both have 3.88. The lowest mean of 3.53 belongs to the 'research for proper references for child protection topics to be integrated'. The table shows that the teachers are generally 'capable' of integrating the child protection policy into their classrooms. This is important to the role of teachers as implementors of the CPP.

Table 11. Kruskal Wallis H-Test: Differences in the Level of Knowledge, Attitude, and the Level of Capability of the Respondents to Integrate the CPP into their Classroom When Grouped According to Age

Indicator	Age Group	Mean Rank	H-value	P-value	Decision	Remarks
Level of Knowledge about Child Protection Policy	20-25 years old	129.22	3.988	0.678	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	26-30 years old	113.18				
	31-35 years old	113.27				
	36-40 years old	100.99				
	41-45 years old	98.86				
	46-50 years old	116.85				
	51 and above	106.73				
	20-25 years old	148.56	15.721	0.015	Reject Ho	Significant

Attitude Toward Integrating Child Protection Policy Into Your Classrooms	26-30 years old	114.79	11.139	0.084	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	31-35 years old	122.00				
	36-40 years old	95.61				
	41-45 years old	96.99				
	46-50 years old	124.25				
51 and above	89.94					
Level of Capability to Integrate Child Protection Policy Into Your Classrooms	20-25 years old	147.39				
	26-30 years old	117.53				
	31-35 years old	115.12				
	36-40 years old	107.33				
	41-45 years old	90.61				
Classrooms	46-50 years old	115.27				
	51 and above	93.12				

Legend: If the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.

The findings indicate that there is no statistically significant variation in teachers' knowledge of CPP based on age groups, suggesting that both age and experience do not contribute to a higher level of knowledge of the CPP. This can be viewed as a beneficial aspect for young teachers who may have less expertise in implementing CPP. Conversely, teachers who have been teaching in public schools since the first introduction of the CPP twelve years ago are anticipated to possess a more advanced level of understanding regarding the CPP. The grand mean of the respondents on their level of knowledge about CPP is 3.52 which is just .02 higher than the mean for moderate knowledge. Thus, interventions must be conducted for all teachers regardless of their profile to better their knowledge of CPP. Moreover, the findings indicate that despite the varying mean ranks for age groups on their capability to integrate CPP into their classrooms, the hypothesis is not rejected. Thus, all teachers across different age brackets show a similar level of capability.

Although the respondents' level of attitude towards integrating CPP in the classroom is generally 'Agree', their attitude is significantly different according to age with the oldest age having the lowest mean rank. This suggests that younger teachers have a more positive attitude toward the integration of CPP into their classroom practices compared to older age groups.

Table 12: Kruskal Wallis H-Test: Differences in the Level of Knowledge, Attitude, and the Level of Capability of the Respondents to Integrate the CPP into their Classrooms When Grouped According to Civil Status

Indicator	Civil Status	Mean Rank	H-value	P-value	Decision	Remarks
Level of Knowledge about Child Protection Policy	single	117.04	2.874	0.411	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	married	105.07				
	widow/widower	82.25				
	separated/annulled	119.33				

Attitude Toward Integrating Child Protection Policy Into Your Classrooms	single	117.49	5.687	0.128	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	married	104.05				
	widow/widower	81.88				
	separated/annulled	158.17				
Level of Capability to Integrate Child Protection Policy Into Your Classrooms	single	116.65	2.975	0.395	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	married	104.70				
	widow/widower	90.50				
	separated/annulled	134.50				

Legend: If the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.

Table 12 illustrates that there is no significant difference in the level of knowledge, attitude, and capability to integrate CPP into the classroom when the respondents are grouped according to civil status. The results show that teachers' knowledge, attitude, and capability to integrate CPP into their classroom practices are not influenced by their civil status. This finding is encouraging as it suggests that teachers, regardless of their marital status, do not show significant differences in their knowledge, attitude, and capability to integrate CPP. In practical terms, capacity programs and support mechanisms can be generically drafted, taking into account a consistent baseline of knowledge, attitude, and capability.

Table 13. Kruskal Wallis H-Test: Differences in the Level of Knowledge, Attitude, and the Level of Capability of the Respondents to Integrate the CPP into their Classrooms When Grouped According to their School Deployment

Indicator	School	Mean Rank	H-value	P-value	Decision	Remarks
Level of Knowledge about Child Protection Policy	Ampid NHS	106.34	26.767	>0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	Guinayang NHS	77.11				
	Jose F. Diaz NHS	115.95				
	Pintong Bukawe NHS	126.89				
	San Mateo NHS	96.18				
	Silangan NHS	138.69				
Attitude Toward Integrating Child Protection Policy Into Your Classrooms	Ampid NHS	108.59	9.688	0.085	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Guinayang NHS	95.98				
	Jose F. Diaz NHS	107.23				
	Pintong Bukawe NHS	111.44				
	San Mateo NHS	99.22				
	Silangan NHS	128.58				
	Ampid NHS	111.53	29.965	>0.000	Reject Ho	Significant

Level of Capability to Integrate Child Protection Policy Into Your Classrooms	Guinayang NHS	81.75
	Jose F. Diaz NHS	108.10
	Pintong Bukawe NHS	130.06
	San Mateo NHS	92.01
	Silangan NHS	141.07

Legend: If the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.

Table 13 shows that there is no significant difference in the level of attitude towards integrating child protection policy into the classrooms when the respondents are grouped according to the school where they teach. This can be looked at positively considering that the grand mean for the respondents' attitude towards integrating CPP is high at 4.00 which is verbally interpreted as agree. However, there is a significant difference in the level of knowledge about child protection policy and in the level of capability to integrate child protection policy in the classroom. Thus, Ho is accepted for the level of attitude while the decisions for the level of knowledge and capability are 'reject Ho'.

The result shows that although there is no significant difference in attitude, the difference in knowledge and capability emphasizes the need to study the cause of variances. The teachers in higher San Mateo must have received more effective training and support in child protection policy or it could be about their school climate. Thus, a focused capacity-building program drafted to target the gaps in knowledge and capability within the schools in lower San Mateo is a necessity.

Table 14. Kruskal Wallis H-Test: Differences in the Level of Knowledge, Attitude, and the Level of Capability of the Respondents to Integrate the CPP into their Classrooms When Grouped According to Subject Department

Indicator	Subject	Mean Rank	H-value	P-value	Decision	Remarks
Level of Knowledge about Child Protection Policy	English	109.04	12.283	0.092	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Filipino	103.85				
	Mathematics	97.44				
	TLE/ICT	98.45				
	Science	102.47				
	ESP	133.13				
	Social Studies	127.16				
Attitude Toward Integrating Child Protection Policy Into Your Classrooms	English	108.22	19.416	0.007	Reject Ho	Significant
	Filipino	120.74				
	Mathematics	111.64				
	TLE/ICT	97.25				
	Science	92.54				
	ESP	147.33				
	Social Studies	109.54				

	MAPEH	87.27				
Level of Capability to Integrate Child Protection Policy Into Your Classrooms	English	117.76	3.619	0.822	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Filipino	113.76				
	Mathematics	97.56				
	TLE/ICT	105.57				
	Science	103.41				
	ESP	112.83				
	Social Studies	115.47				
	MAPEH	96.00				

Legend: If the *p*-value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.

Table 14 demonstrates that there is no significance in the level of knowledge and the level of capability to integrate CPP of the teachers when they are grouped according to the subject they teach. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the level of knowledge and their capability to integrate CPP when they are grouped according to the subject that they teach. This is in contrast to the study of dela Fuente (2021) which concluded that there is enough evidence to show that there is a significant difference in the teachers' awareness of child protection policy when they are grouped according to their specialization. However, for the attitude toward integrating child protection policy, the decision is that the Ho is rejected so there is a significant difference in the attitude of teachers toward the integration of child protection policy into the classroom when they are grouped according to the subject they teach. The highest mean rank comes from the teachers of ESP or Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao while the MAPEH teachers' mean rank is the lowest.

Table 15. Kruskal Wallis H-Test: Differences in the Level of Knowledge, Attitude, and the Level of Capability of the Respondents to Integrate CPP into their Classroom when Grouped According to the Highest Educational Attainment

Indicator	Highest Educational Attainment	Mean Rank	H-value	P-value	Decision	Remarks
Level of Knowledge about Child Protection Policy	BSE/BSED	112.86	7.389	0.286	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	BS with CPE units	98.50				
	with MAED/MSE/MAT units	101.54				
	MAED/MSE/MAT/MPA graduate	124.10				
	with Ed.D/ Ph.D or units	149.00				
	Others	103.80				
Attitude Toward Integrating Child Protection Policy Into	BSE/BSED	112.63	1.694	0.946	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	BS with CPE units	114.31				
	with MAED/MSE/MAT units	109.23				
	MAED/MSE/MAT/MPA graduate	103.02				

Your Classrooms	with Ed.D/ Ph.D or units	100.50	4.521	0.607	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Others	83.90				
Level of Capability to Integrate Child Protection Policy Into Your Classrooms	BSE/BSED	116.48				
	BS with CPE units	116.13				
	with MAED/MSE/MAT units	101.87				
Your Classrooms	MAED/MSE/MAT/MPA graduate	115.83				
	with Ed.D/ Ph.D or units	134.50				
	Others	99.30				

Legend: If the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho

Table 15 indicates that there is no significant difference in the level of knowledge, the level of attitude, and the level of capability to integrate child protection policy into the classroom when the teacher respondents are grouped according to their highest educational attainment. This contrasts with the study of Rabina (2019) which found that the teachers' educational qualification is significantly related to their awareness of child protection policy. The grand means for knowledge, attitude, and capability of the respondents are above average, the 'not significant' remark can be looked at positively.

Knowing that teachers at all educational levels are approximately the same in terms of knowledge, attitude, and capability is reassuring. This suggests that teachers, regardless of whether they possess a bachelor's degree or a doctoral degree, have a comparable fundamental understanding of CPP. This suggests that the effectiveness of training programs provided to teachers, regardless of their educational backgrounds, may be a contributing factor to their success. Similarly, the educational attainment of teachers does not impact their attitudes and capabilities.

Table 16. Kruskal Wallis H-Test: Differences in the Level of Knowledge, Attitude, and the Level of Capability of the Respondents to Integrate the CPP in their Classrooms when Grouped According to Position

Indicator	Position	Mean Rank	H-value	P-value	Decision	Remarks
Level of Knowledge about Child Protection Policy	Teacher I	101.21	6.797	0.147	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher II	119.31				
	Teacher III	123.70				
	Master Teachers	114.17				
Attitude Toward Integrating Child Protection Policy	Teacher I	104.29	4.491	0.344	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher II	114.41				
	Teacher III	118.58				

Into Your Classrooms	Master Teachers	114.92				
Level of Capability to Integrate Child Protection Policy Into Your Classrooms	Teacher I	102.24	6.389	0.172	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher II	122.40				
	Teacher III	119.09				
	Master Teachers	101.83				

Legend: If the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.

Table 17 shows that there is no significant difference in the level of knowledge, attitude, and capability to integrate CPP into classrooms when grouped according to their position. This contrasts with the study of Rabina (2019) which gathered enough evidence to show that there is a significant difference in the awareness of child protection policy when the respondents are grouped according to their position with the respondents occupying the highest position showing the higher extent of awareness.

The non-significant difference in the knowledge, attitude, and capability of the teachers to integrate child protection policies when they are grouped according to their position shows that teachers have collective knowledge and perception of the importance of child protection policy, and they have comparable practical skills in integrating CPP into their classrooms. The grand means for knowledge, attitude, and capability of respondents are beyond average so this can be looked at positively. Regardless of position, all teachers are one in wanting to provide an environment where students' rights are respected.

Table 17. Kruskal Wallis H-Test: Differences in the Level of Knowledge, Attitude, and the Level of Capability of the Respondents to Integrate CPP in their Classroom Practices when Grouped According to the Number of Years in Service

Indicator	Number of Years in Service	Mean Rank	H-value	P-value	Decision	Remarks
Level of Knowledge about Child Protection Policy	1-5 years	117.11	6.984	0.072	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	6-10 years	94.30				
	11-15 years	117.43				
	16 years and above	112.53				
Attitude Toward Integrating Child Protection Policy Into Your Classrooms	1-5 years	125.55	9.119	0.028	Reject Ho	Significant
	6-10 years	97.24				
	11-15 years	103.09				
	16 years and above	106.61				
Level of Capability to Integrate Child Protection Policy Into Your Classrooms	1-5 years	130.19	22.594	>0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	6-10 years	84.78				
	11-15 years	115.66				
	16 years and above	110.50				

Legend: If the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.

The table indicates that there is no significant difference in the level of understanding regarding child protection policies among the respondents when they are categorized based on their years of service. Across the different years of service group, the teachers have the same level of knowledge about CPP which is above average since the grand mean is 3.52, verbally interpreted as 'knowledgeable'. However, a contrasting pattern emerges regarding the attitude and the capability to integrate child protection policy in classrooms when categorized based on years of service.

Just like there is no significant difference between knowledge in CPP and the age of the respondents, there is also no significant difference between knowledge in CPP and the number of years in service. As explained earlier, this assures a consistent baseline knowledge among all teachers. The significant difference between the teachers' attitude towards CPP and their number of years in service is also aligned with the significant difference between their attitude toward CPP and their age. The table is indicative of the varying attitudes of the teachers at different stages of their careers. The same can be said about their capability to integrate CPP.

Conclusions

The results show that teachers' level of knowledge about the child protection policy was verbally interpreted as 'Knowledgeable'. The teachers' attitude towards integrating child protection policy into their classroom practices was verbally interpreted as "Agree". The teachers' level of capability to integrate child protection policy in their classroom practices was verbally interpreted as "Capable".

Moreover, the difference between the respondents' knowledge and their profiles was not significant except for the school where they taught. The difference between the respondents' attitude and their age, the subject they taught, and the number of years in service were significant. However, the difference between their attitude and their civil status, the school where they taught, their highest educational attainment, and their position were not significant. The difference between their capability and their profiles was not significant except for the school where they taught and their number of years in service.

Recommendations

In light of the findings, the following recommendations are made: The level of comprehension of other child protection regulations and principles in CPP is very low. Teachers require a particular training program, workshop, or relevant resources to address their deficiencies in understanding child safety legislation and practices. Teachers generally have a favorable disposition towards CPP in the classroom, although there are significant variations according to age. Specialized training and awareness programs tailored for elderly individuals are necessary to highlight the integration of CPP. The abilities, tenure, and schools of teachers exhibit significant differences. Considering

that instructors who have been serving for six to ten years have the lowest average rank, it is crucial to offer personalized professional development opportunities that strongly emphasize CPP. On the other hand, every school needs evaluation programs to pinpoint its deficiencies. Integration activities are proposed to address the significant disparity between teachers' views and their subjects. Utilizing modeling techniques and providing subject-specific examples can aid teachers in comprehending the advantages of integrating CPP across a wide range of topics.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study followed the ethical guidelines for conducting research with teacher respondents. Prior to commencing the data collection process, the researcher made certain that informed consent was acquired from all participants. The participants were provided with information regarding the study's objective, the utilization of the data, and the voluntary aspect of their involvement. In addition, the participants' information was ensured to be confidential, and any identifiable data was eliminated during the data processing phase to safeguard their privacy.

Acknowledgments

The author wishes to thank the COED-Graduate School of the Polytechnic University of the Philippines for the guidance in the conduct and completion of this study. The SDS of the Division of Rizal, the principals, and the teachers where the study was conducted are also acknowledged for taking part in this academic endeavor. Special acknowledgment for the School Head of Guinayang National High School, the Child Protection Committee, and the Research Committee of the same school who helped finished this study.

REFERENCES

- Arts, K. (2013). Countering violence against children in the Philippines: positive RBA practice examples from Plan. In *Human Rights and Development in the new Millennium* (pp. 161-188). Routledge.
- Asio, J. M. R., A Bayucca, S., & Jimenez, E. (2020). Child protection policy awareness of teachers and responsiveness of the school: Their relationship and implications. *Asio, JMR*,
- BARONIA, JOHN MELDWIN B. "Perception of elementary school heads and teachers on child protection policy in private schools in Tanauan City Division." *IOER International Multidisciplinary Research Journal* 2, no. 2 (2020): 35-45.
- Bayucca, S. A. (2020). Teachers' Awareness and School's Responsiveness to the Child Protection Policy: Basis for a Development Plan. *Online Submission*, 4(6), 59-65.
- Bayucca, SA, & Jimenez, EC (2020). *Child protection policy awareness of teachers and responsiveness of the school: Their relationship and implications. Shanlax International Journal of Education*, 9(1), 1-10.
- Briggs, F. (2020). *Child protection: A guide for teachers and child care professionals*. Routledge.

- Calderon, J. (2006). *Methods of research and thesis writing* (2nd Ed.). Mandaluyong City: National Bookstore.
- DE VERA, J. P. E. The Creation of Child-Friendly Local Communities Through Local Codes on Children: An Analysis of LCCs in Selected Provinces and Cities in the Philippines.
- dela Fuente, C. L. (2021). Filipino Basic Education Teachers' Awareness of and Attitude towards the Child Protection Policy. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*, 2(1), 39-48.
- Kini, T., & Podolsky, A. (2016). Teaching experience and teacher effectiveness. *American Educator*, 40(3), 3.
- McGarry, K., & Buckley, H. (2013). Lessons on child protection: a survey of newly qualified primary-level teachers in Ireland. *Child abuse review*, 22(2), 80-92.
- Morante, M. (2017). Implementation of the Child Protection Policy in Selected Schools of District IV in the Division of Parañaque: Base Reference for Intervention Program.
- Oducado, R. M. (2020). Survey instrument validation rating scale. Available at SSRN 3789575.
- Pagayanan, R. P. (2021). CAREER ADVANCEMENT STAGNATION AMONG PUBLIC SCHOOL TEACHERS IN TACLOBAN CITY: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY. *CAREER ADVANCEMENT STAGNATION AMONG PUBLIC SCHOOL TEACHERS IN TACLOBAN CITY: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY*, 79(1), 11-11.
- RABINA, A. A. (2019). *School Heads and Teachers' Awareness of the Child Protection Policy: A Basis for a Training Program* (Doctoral dissertation, Foundation University).
- UNICEF. (2012). Child Protection in Educational Settings: Findings from Six Countries in East Asia and the Pacific.
- Vural, Ö. F., & Başaran, M. (2021). The reasons for teachers' preference for Master's degree: Teachers' preference for Master's degree. *International Journal of Curriculum and Instruction*, 13(1), 589-613.
- Walsh, K., Mathews, B., Rassafiani, M., Farrell, A., & Butler, D. (2013). Elementary teachers' knowledge of legislative and policy duties for reporting child sexual abuse. *The Elementary School Journal*, 114(2), 178-199.
- Zabala, B., and Lachica, H. (2018). Status of work values of elementary school teachers in congressional district I, division of Nueva Ecija. *International Journal of Research in Sociology and Anthropology*, 4 (2), 40-51.
- The Kempe Foundation. (2023 March 27). The Role of Educators in Child Abuse and Neglect Prevention. <https://kempe.org/2023/03/27/the-role-of-educators-in-child-abuse-neglect-prevention/>
-